

TOURISM DEVELOPMENT NASHIK CITY AND TRIMBAKESHWAR– A MICRO STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

A long back not much attention was paid to the importance and development of tourism in the country. Tourism was merely regarded as ones private affair or ones individuals joy or happy. But how it is not so, tourism is not only a good industry in the field of economic development but equally an important medium for international Socio- cultural links. In India “National Tourism Policy was formed in the year 1982. The main aim behind this policy on tourism was give a new sense of purpose and section to the development and promotion to tourism and add new direction to it.

Keywords: Tourism, National Tourism, Hotel Industry, Employment opportunities.

INTRODUCTION:

Tourism and hotel industry are inter- related or go hand in hand if tourism develops the hotel industry also develops and vice versa, and with the help of tourism we can earn foreign exchange without export investment or without capital. Tourism was the largest net foreign exchange earner according to the Reserve Bank statistics. In a country like India tourism play vital role for economy. Tourism helps national integrity and it also provides employment opportunities.

In Maharashtra, Nashik and Trimbakeshwar are two places namely chosen for the study.

Objectives:-

1. To Study the personal factors of tourist in Nashik and Trimbakeshwar
2. To study the motivational factors of the tourist in Trimbakeshwar and Nashik
3. To offer suggestion for satisfaction of the tourist based on filed work of the study.

Database and Research Methodology

For this research purpose and for effective presentation of the study primary data was taken or primary data has been obtained from the tourists who have visited in the tourist spots in and around Nashik and Trimbakeshwar through structured interview schedule. Secondary data has been collected from statistical department, MTDC (Maharashtra Tourism Development Corporation).

The study is based on Sampling for the purpose of the study 75 Indian tourist of different parts of the India have been selected by around Nashik and Trimbakeshwar as shown in Table 1.

The table 1 shows that the respondents classified under the four heads namely official, personal, business and tourism. The number of respondents is 10, 25, 10 and 30

Table No 1

Purpose of Visit	Respondents No	
Official	10	13.33
Personal	25	33.33
Business	10	13.33
Tourism	30	40
Total	75	100

Source:- Primary data

Importance of Nashik Tourism Development

The development of Tourism is any part of the world mainly depends on the pleasant climatic conditions, relief features such as mountain, river valley, waterfalls, wild life, dams, vegetation and religious importance, well connected transportation facilities all these factors responsible for the development of tourism in Nashik district.

Study Area:-

Nashik district lies between $19^{\circ} 35'$ & $20^{\circ} 52'$ N Latitudes and $73^{\circ} 16'$ & $74^{\circ} 56'$ East Longitude with an area of 15530 sq kms. The district consists 15 tehsils. It is surrounded by Jalgaon district in the east and north east, Dhule district in the north, Dang and Surat districts of Gujarat state to the North West. Ahmednagar district to the south and Aurangabad district to the south west.

Important Places around Nashik City and Trimbakeshwar

The Kalaram Temple:-

The Kalaram Temple is an old Hindu shrine dedicated to Rama in the Panchavati area of Nashik city in Maharashtra. The temple derives its name from the statue of Lord Rama that is black. The literal translation of Kalaram means black Rama. The sanctum sanctorum also houses the statues of goddess Sita and god Lakshmana. Thousands of devotees visit it every day. The temple was built by Sardar Rangarao Odhekar in 1788.

Kapaleshwar Temple:-

Kapaleshwar Temple built in 1763 located near Ramkund Panchavati and the holy river Godavari. The temple name Kapaleshwar mean Kapalam meaning head and eshwara another name for Shiva. A Unique aspect of this temple not seen in any other Shiva temples is the lack of a Nandi in front of the Shiva lingam. Shravani Somvar (Monday) and Shivratri are two day when pilgrims gather in large numbers in this temple

MuktidhamS

Muktidham is a marble temple complex honouring various gods. It is popular tourist attraction situated in the Nashik Road. It is privately operated through a trust and was built through a generous donation by the late Mr. J. D. Chauhan - Bytco a local industrialist. The temple was built in 1971. Muktidham is amongst the tourist attraction of town. Because all the idols of all major Hindu Gods are placed in a one roof.

Pandavleni:-

This caves are 2000 years old and it was built by the Jain kings. It is a group of 24 Hinayana Buddhist Caves.

Table No- 2 Motivation of Tourism

No	Motivational Category	Motivations
01	Physical Motivations	Refreshment of body and mind for health purpose, Participation in sports activity, Pleasure, Fun, Excitement, Romance and entertain to shop.
02	Cultural Motivations	Curiosity about foreign countries, people and places in different parts, Intrest in art, music architecture, folk, intrest in historical placed. Sports such as fifa world cup, Olympic games etc.
03	Personal Motivations	Visiting relatives and friends, meeting new people and seeking new friendship seeking new and different experiences in different environments, escaping from one's own permanent social environment (i.e. desire for change) personal excitement of travelling visiting places and people for spiritual reasons.
04	Prestige and Status Motivations	Persuit hobbies continuation of education or learning seeking of business contacts and professional goals conferences and meeting, ego, enhancement and sensual indulgence fashion.

Table No-3 –Profile of Respondents

Factors	No	%	Factors	No	%
Gender			Income per Month (In Rs)		
Male	55	61.11	Below -10000	10	16.67
Female	35	38.88	1000-20000	20	33.33
Age Group			2000-30000	20	33.33
Up to 35 Years	25	35.71	Above -30000	10	16.67
Above 35 Years	45	64.28	No of Times Visited		
Occupation			First Time	12	24.49
Blue Collor	08	9.3	Second Time	22	44.90
White Collor	06	6.9	Third Time and More	15	30.61
Professional	12	13.9	Staying With or Without their family		
Businessman	15	17.44	Alone	15	42.86
Home makes	19	22.09	With Family	20	57.14

Land Owners	17	19.77	Different State Tourist		
Non-Earning Member	09	10.47	Karnataka	06	10.16
			Gujarat	14	23.73
			M. Pradesh	08	13.56
			Maharashtra	22	37.29
			Others	09	15.25

Table No- 4 Purpose of visit Vs Motivational factors

Purpose of Visit	Physical Motivation		Cultural Motivation		Personal Motivation		Prestige & Status Motivation		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Official	04	40	02	20	03	30	01	10	10	100
Personal	12	48	06	24	04	16	03	12	25	100
Business	02	20	04	40	01	10	03	30	10	100
Tourism	08	26.67	07	23.33	05	16.67	10	33.33	30	100

Source: - Based on Field Survey

Table No -5 Purpose of Visit Vs Places Seen in Nearby Nashik and Trimbakeshwar by the tourist respondents

Purpose of visit	Tourist Places							
	K.T	Ka.T	N.T	M.Dham	P.Lani	C.Lani	Tapovan	T.Keshwar
Official	04	03	-	10	02	-	03	10
Personal	06	07	-	12	04	04	08	16
Business	05	02	-	14	-	-	02	19
Tourism	17	20	04	28	07	06	12	23
Total	32	33	04	64	13	10	25	68

Source: - Based on Field Survey

K.T (Kalaram Temple), Ka.T. (Kapaleshwar Temple), N.T. (Naro Shankar Temple), M. Dham.(Muktidham), P.Leni. (Pandav Leni)

Comparison of Hotel Facility in Nashik City and Trimbakashwar with their state /place

States	Highly Satisfied		Satisfied		Dis Satisfied		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Karnataka	02	33.33	03	50	01	16.66	06	100
Gujarat	07	50	05	35.71	02	14.28	14	100
M.pradesh	05	62.5	03	37.5	-	-	08	100
Maharashtra	12	54.54	07	31.81	03	13.63	22	100
Others	03	33.33	04	44.44	02	22.22	09	100

Source :- Primary Data

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The analysis reveals that the table No 4 indicate that most of the respondents visited Trimbakeshwar, Kalaram Temple, Tapovan, Muktidham respondents fall under the purpose of Tourism and neglect to visit other than Naroshankar Temple, Pandav Leni, Chamar Leni etc.

From the table No -3 it is clear that out of 90 respondents 61% are mainly male and 38.88 % are female. 64.28% are fall under the category of more than 35 years and remaining 35.71 are less than 35 years. With regards to occupation Homemakers account of 19% followed by land owner 17 % and then 15% are businessmen. most of the respondents income group comes Rs 10,000 to 30,000 are 66.66% while out of 35 respondents 42.86% of them staying alone and remaining 57.14% with their family. As it is clear that from table No-3. Most of tourist comes from within a state and othertourist comes from Gujarat most of the tourist from other parts are satisfied while 13-22% of the respondents from other state expressed dissatisfaction.

Conclusion and Suggestion:-

It is evident from the study that the tourism department (ITDC), hotel industry and travel agents need to develop a good network to attract traveler's interest. As well as also providing the detail information about the new tourist spot seem to access the web to identify the idea destination for their visits. There is a potential of the agro tourism in Nashik district. Agro tourism helps to encourage and support the diversity of local economies for which tourism related income is important.

References

1. Maharashtra BhugolShastraSanshodhanPatrika- Vol XXXIX, No.1,P 38-41
2. District Gazetteer of Nashik District (1994)
3. Census Handbook of Nashik District (2001)
4. S.Kumar Das (2006) Research Methodology in Tourism, ABD Publisher, Jaipur.

5. Foundation of Tourism Development by Negi, Jagmoahan.
6. Khatib K,A., Geography of Tourism, Meththa Publications, Kolhapur.
7. GharpureVittal (2001) Geography of Tourism, Pimplapure and Co. Publication Nagpur.
8. Bhatia: International Tourism,
9. Shinde S.,B.(1997)Geography of Tourism (Marathi) Phadake Publication, Kolhapur
10. Socio-Economic Review 2009.